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Cover: Lakshmi as one of the consorts of Vishnu, Kawaimari, Kapili-Jamuna Valley

Back Cover: Lakshmi, Sankyadevi, Kapili-Jamuna Valley

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An Analysis of the Sacred Geography of Śrīvaiṣṇavas using modern GIS with reference to the 108 Divyadeśam Temples

Sanjay S*

Śrīvaiṣṇavism one of the *Vaiṣṇava* sects of Hinduism originating from South India and dating back to the 12th century CE and is confined primarily to Tamil Nadu and southern parts of Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka. This tradition considers *Viṣṇu* as their supreme godhead and was propagated through religious teachers called *Ācāryapuruṣās* who in turn were influenced by the devotional hymns and songs written by a group of saints known as the *Ālvārs* (Rajaraajan 2013: 37-90). These saints were a part of the revitalization movement that developed within Hinduism called *Bhakti*, characterised by their simple but impassioned messages and their implied egalitarian bias (Spencer 1970: 232-244). Pilgrimage in the *Srīvaiṣṇava* community today is a normative concept as well as a religious practice (Dutta 2010: 17-38). Their surviving devotional literature in the form of hagiographies is rich in specific geographical references, most of which can be precisely identified on modern maps.

The sacred geography of the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* comprises traditionally of 108 sites called *Divyadeśams* literally meaning 'holy places' of which 106 are terrestrial with one in Nepal and the others in India while the last two sites are celestial in nature. This paper aims to attempt a geographical analysis of the terrestrial *Divyadeśam* sites using GIS softwares in relation to their traditional classifications based on the political divisions that existed in the past. The list of places visited by the *Ālvārs* during their lifetime along with the present names of the sites and temple locations were identified from books and research articles (Kumaran 2021). While the coordinates

for plotting the sites on a map were obtained using the Google maps application, the distance of the traditional political divisions was measured using Google Earth. As many of the temples recorded in the hymns of these saints have architectural features that were built, restored, and rebuilt from time to time a proper classification regarding the ages of the monumental structures present today could not be attempted.

Bhakti and Śrīvaiṣṇavism

Revitalization movements are subjects of special interest to both historians and social scientists as such trends have provided scholars with useful data for the study of political, social, and religious change (Stein 1997: 7-26). *Śrīvaiṣṇavism* is one such unique tradition that was founded on the core principles of Hinduism but at the same time carved out a separate set of theological principles and practices quite different from the rest (Iyengar 2009). The period of Pallava political ascendancy from roughly the sixth through the ninth centuries CE saw the crystallization of many forms of thought and action which would prevail in the Tamil country in later centuries (Spencer 1970: 232-244).

The new advocates of devotionism in the form of Hindu *Bhakti* and the proclaimed founders of *Śrīvaiṣṇavism* were the 12 *Ālvārs* i.e., those who 'plunged into the divine' (Iyengar 2009). This revitalized form of Hinduism which the saints articulated emphasized salvation through simple but impassioned devotion to God which allowed equal participation to members from

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the lower classes and also to women, whose standing in society was reduced in the post-Vedic times (Spencer 1970: 232-244). In fact, the *Ālvārs* themselves came from all aspects of life and belonged to different castes.

The assigning of correct dates for these saints is a difficult task which has been made even harder by the fact that all later *Srivaishnava* literature has given them the status of being emanations of *Viṣṇu's* attributes themselves. Poykai *Ālvār*, Pūtam *Ālvār* and Pēy *Ālvār* who are all believed to have lived in c. 7th century CE are collectively called as *Mudhal Ālvārs* or the first *Ālvārs*. Tirumalīcai *Ālvār* (7th century CE), Toṅṅaraṭṭipōṭi *Ālvār*, Tiruppāṇ *Ālvār*, and Kulacēkarar *Ālvār* are all believed to have lived in the c. 8th century CE while Periyālvār, Āṅṅāl (the only female saint), and Maturakavi *Ālvār* are all considered to have lived in the c. 9th century CE (Kumaran 2021).

The devotional songs of the *Ālvārs* in the form of hymns to worship *Viṣṇu* and his other incarnations or *avatars* were said to have been collected only in the 10th century CE after being originally lost. This later compilation done by the scholar-saint Nadhamuni is what presently survives and is referred to as the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam*. Written entirely in Tamil it is considered to be the foundational text of *Śrīvaiṣṇavism*. Each temple referenced by the *Ālvārs*, has a minimum of one verse in the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam*, extolling the significance of the presiding deity, the mythical origins of the temple as a locale for sacred deeds and miracles while also ascribing spiritual rewards and redemption for worshippers of the site (Iyengar 2009).

The post-*Ālvār* stage in *Śrīvaiṣṇavism* was started by the eleventh-century philosopher Rāmānujā who is mainly credited with making Srirangam the epicentre for *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* and with preventing the *Bhakti* movement from degenerating into a purely subjective emotion by reinterpreting ancient texts like the *Vedas* to defend theism and religion of the heart (Pande 1996: 110-120). The charting out of a comprehensive pilgrimage network comprising of 108 shrines and a visit to each of them also appeared prominently in the later biographical narrative of Rāmānujā (Dutta 2010: 17-38). Thus, this wayfaring narrative of his combined with the previous extolling of sites by the *Ālvārs* gave importance to the articulation of the sacred geography for *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* and in many ways marked the physical and spiritual

boundary defining the community for whom the concept of pilgrimage was first enunciated in the twelfth-century hagiographical text, the *Divyāsūricaritam*, composed by one Garudavahanapandita (Dutta 2010: 17-38).

Here a clear distinction must be made between *Vaiṣṇavism* and *Śrīvaiṣṇavism*. *Viṣṇuism/Vaiṣṇavism* took its roots in Vedic lore and reached its zenith in the hymns of the *Ālvārs* where *Viṣṇu* became the focal point of attention and *Śrīvaiṣṇavism* as a codified system of philosophy developed in the 12th century only after the time of Rāmānujā, with the focal point of *Viṣṇu* being mediated through *Śrī* (Rajarajan 2013: 37-90). Hence the *Ālvārs* did not call themselves *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* but rather concentrated their effort on bringing to the forefront the utmost devotion one could profess to *Viṣṇu*.

By the end of the twelfth century however, there came to be two doctrinal schools among the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* namely *Vatakalai* and *Tenkalai* emerging as a result of two main issues which became points of conflict and debate. One was the question of the successors of Rāmānujā which centred on the identity of the legitimate descendant and two was the theological issues bordering on soteriological differences (Pande 1996: 110-120). The *Vatakalai* or the 'northern school' came to be centred in the areas of Kanchipuram and Thiruvananthapuram and the *Tenkalai* or 'southern school' retained their centre as Srirangam, though in reality there is no geographical polarization to justify this nomenclature as there are no texts nor epigraphs that make mentions to such affiliations (Pande 1996: 110-120).

The Importance of Pilgrimage to the Divyadeśam Temples for Śrīvaiṣṇavas

In the Hindu tradition, the idea of the divine is embodied in multiple layers of natural and man-made geography. The 106 *Divyadeśam* temples are one of the most prestigious symbols of identity to the *Srivaishnava* community as these temples are constantly referred to in their tradition as '*Bhuloka Vaikuntam*' which in Sanskrit quite literally means 'heaven on earth' (Iyengar 2009). The journey to the *Srivaishnava* shrines, emerged as a dominant motif in *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam*, so much so that the area of hymnal composition as well as the enactment of certain biographical events of the *Ālvārs* happened to be the temple sites themselves (Dutta 2010: 17-38). These temples being exalted by the *Ālvārs* became epicentres of

Fig. 1: The 106 Divyadeśam Temples as per the Nālāyiratīvyāpīrapantam

theological study and the only places to have historically celebrated *Srīvaiṣṇava* festivals (Iyengar 2009). In fact, a *Srīvaiṣṇava* hopes to visit all the 106 temples at least once during his or her lifetime, as a pilgrimage in the *Srīvaiṣṇava* textual tradition ‘delineates a cognitive as well as an ideational sacred space that reflects a single uniform community, focused on the worship of *Viṣṇu*’ (Dutta 2010: 17-38) (Fig. 1).

The 106 Terrestrial Divyadeśam Temples

The 106 terrestrial temples in the *Nālāyiratīvyāpīrapantam* were divided into 6 divisions based on the political boundaries that existed from the c. 7th to the 10th century CE. They are:

- 1) *Chola Nadu* with 40 temples
- 2) *Nadu Naadu* with 2 temples
- 3) *Thondai Nadu* with 22 temples

- 4) *Vada Nadu* with 11 temples
- 5) *Malai Nadu* with 13 temples
- 6) *Pandiya Nadu* with 18 temples

In the hymns of the *Ālvārs*, the temples represented in concrete terms the divine presence within structural shrines, making *Viṣṇu* accessible in a specific place to everybody irrespective of their caste status (Dutta 2010: 17-38). The two celestial sites namely *Pārkaṭal* (the ocean of milk) and *Paramapadam* (*Vaikunṭha*) were associated with the heavenly adobe of *Viṣṇu*, which a person could enter only after the end of their life. For a list of the entire 106 Temples and their coordinates used to plot on the map check the appendix section of this paper.

The modern-day identification of the sites mentioned in the *Nālāyiratīvyāpīrapantam* by scholars of the past (Hardy 1983) was enabled by the vivid descriptions of the typology of the various sites based on natural landscape

as well as the iconography of the deity in the hymns themselves, for example, certain areas were said to be surrounded by groves and forests (Thirumaaliruncholai of Pandiya Nadu), certain areas were on the hills (Vengadam of Vada Nadu), some areas were surrounded by water (Thiruvarangam of Chola Nadu), some were prosperous cities (Thirukkurgur of Pandiya Nadu), and some were prosperous agrarian settlements (Tiruvananthapuram of Malai Nadu) (Dutta 2010: 17-38).

In today's terms, *Thondai Nadu* can be identified with the northern parts of Tamil Nadu while *Chola Nadu* corresponds to the Kaveri deltaic region. The area in between them is the *Nadu Naadu* region, with the southern parts of Tamil Nadu and Kerala corresponding to the divisions of *Pandiya Nadu* and *Malai Nadu* respectively.

The temples coming under *Vada Nadu* include two from Andhra Pradesh and nine others north of the Vindhyas. It is believed that the temples of *Vada Nadu* mentioned beyond the present-day Andhra Pradesh appear to be mere ideational references done by the *Ālvārs* without visiting them personally but to have included them in the 108 *Divyadeśam* temples to attribute a pan-Indian status to *Vaiṣṇavism* (Dutta 2010: 17-38).

A spatial analysis of the temples from *Chola Nadu*, *Tondai Nadu*, *Malai Nadu*, and *Pandiya Nadu* is attempted here using QGIS and Google Earth application to (i) plot the sites mentioned in the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam* accurately using satellite data; and to (ii) know how much area each traditional boundary may have occupied as per the locations of the temples given in the text. *Nadu Naadu*

Figure. 2: Chola Nadu Divya Desam Temples plotted in QGIS

Fig. 3: Spatial Analysis of Srivaisnava Chola Nada using Google Earth

and *Vada Nadu* temple sites were not plotted separately to calculate boundary data as the former consists of only two temples very near to each other while the latter consists of temples very far from each other (Figs. 2-3).

Analysis

The sacred geography of the *Ālvārs* as composed in their hymns is found to be comprised of primarily the Tamil-speaking region from Tirupati to Madurai, and from Cape Comorin to the southwest coast of Kerala, including Kanyakumari and Coimbatore. From Tirupati to Madurai there is a uniform density of *Divyadeśam* temples but this density of sites reduces south of Madurai. The *Divyadeśam* sites don't seem to include a large part of the hinterland that is the central parts of Tamil Nadu and Kerala. These *Śrīvaiṣṇava* holy sites when plotted on a map are identified to be areas nearer to rivers and tracts of water. Such areas near waterbodies could have been

preferred for temple construction due to their fertility and their nature to support dense populations. These sites may have also enabled the movement of people through water-based transport systems which in turn could have allowed *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* from all over to undertake a pilgrimage to these sacred shrines to strengthen their spatial identity (Dutta 2010: 17-38). The close correspondence of waterbodies to many of the *Divyadeśam* temple sites as noticed in the maps can also be explained due to the historical role played by temples in the organization and maintenance of tanks and irrigation systems (Spencer 1970: 232-244).

Plotting the terrestrial sites on QGIS has brought forward a cluster of temples which can be seen inside each traditional division. The *Chola Nadu* contains a cluster of temples in the Nagapattinam district, *Thondai Nadu* has a cluster in the Kanchipuram district, *Malai Nadu* has a cluster along the edges of Pathanamthitta, Kottayam and

Alappuzha districts, while *Pandiya Nadu* has a cluster in the Thoothukudi district. These temple cluster sites were all big towns in the past and as such were centres where major roads connected, making the temples grow rich, powerful, and attractive to pilgrimage and patronage. A large corpus of epigraphs in these temple clusters reveal the focus of Kanchipuram, Srirangam and Tirupathi as major pilgrimage sites throughout the 13th to the 17th century CE, showing that regardless of distance all the temple sites were a single loosely integrated entity (Dutta 2010: 17-38)

Though the *Nālāyirativiyapirapantam* attributes *Chola Nadu* to have the greatest number of temples, area wise *Pandiya Nadu* seems to be most spread out as it comprises a combined area of 14,388.45 km² in comparison to the combined areas of *Chola Nadu* only measuring 5,622.6 km². *Thondai Nadu* has the least

combined area of all the traditional boundaries measuring 3,222.77 km² and *Malai Nadu* has its temple sites spread at a combined area of 5,357.7 km² (Figs. 4-9).

Thanjavur has the greatest number of *Divyadesam* temple sites than any other modern-day district with 18 temples mostly concentrated in the northern half of the district, while the next district with the most *Divyadesam* temple sites is Kanchipuram with 15 temples. This concentration of sacred places within the Thanjavur district is scarcely surprising since its proximity to the Kaveri River has made it one of the most fertile and earliest regions of settled agriculture in Southern India (Spencer 1970: 232-244). Another fact to note in the *Chola Nadu* region is that many of the temple sites are found to be coinciding with major *Brahmadeya* sites which came into existence from the Chola period (Stein 1977: 11-45). *Malai Nadu* temples seem to exist near backwater canals

Figure. 4: Thondai Nadu Divya Desam Temples plotted in QGIS

Figure. 5: Spatial Analysis of Srivaishnava Thondai Nadu using Google Earth

Figure. 6: Malai Nadu Divya Desam Temples plotted in QGIS

Figure. 7: Spatial Analysis of the Srivaisnava Malai Nadu using Google Earth

Figure. 8: Pandiya Nadu Divyadesam Temples plotted in QGIS

Fig. 9: Spatial Analysis of Srivaisnava Pandiya Nadu using Google Earth

while *Pandiya Nadu* combines the regions surrounding the Tamarabarani river valley and the upper Vaigai river.

Though the list of the 108 temples of the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam* starts with *Chola Nadu*, taking into account the birthplaces of the *Ālvārs* as per the text, Hardy hypothesises that the *Vaiṣṇava Bhakti* movement in the Tamil country spread from north to south (Hardy 1983). According to the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam*, *Thondai Nadu* was the birthplace of Tirumaḷicai and the first three *Ālvārs*, *Chola Nadu* and *Malai Nadu* was the birthplace of Tirumaṅkai *Ālvār* and Kulacēkara *Ālvār* respectively while the *Pandiya Nadu* was the birth-place of Nammālvār, Periyālvār, and Āṇṭāl, all resulting in the finding of a good number of *Vaiṣṇavite* shrines springing up into importance around the birth-places of these saints (Chettiar 1941: 42-50). Taking into consideration the traditional chronology and the periodisation of the saints themselves, it is noticed that the first three *Ālvārs* in their hymns, refer to Venkatam (Tirupati) of the *Vada Nadu* along with Mallai (Mahabalipuram) and Thirukkoyalur

of the *Thondai Nadu* as the three important locales of Viṣṇu worship, thus showing that their geographical environment was confined to northern regions of Tamil Nadu with Venkatam as the spiritual centre (Champakalakshmi 1996: 135-163). Next, the hymns of Tirumangai *Ālvār* focuses on the 40 temples of *Chola Nadu* and the hymns of Nammālvār seem to concentrate on the sites present in the *Malai Nadu* division (Dutta 2010). However, in the Hymns of the *Ālvārs* attributed to having lived in the c.9th century, Srirangam emerges as the new geographical and spiritual centre (Champakalakshmi 1996 :135-163). Hence all the above points can give some credence to the postulations of Hardy. Considering the geography pointed out in the *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam*, the *Bhakti* revitalization seems to have emanated and spread in a context of rivalry for social dominance and royal patronage against Buddhism and Jainism as seen by the temple clusters situated in sites like Kanchipuram and regions around Madurai which were historically centres of such religious conflict and change (Champakalakshmi 1996 :135-163).

Conclusion

Śrīvaiṣṇavism is evidence of the evolutionary nature of Hinduism, as this religion in itself was not formed as a rigid set of religious doctrines, but rather as a convergence of various traditions, philosophies, and cultures (Iyengar 2009). The establishment of the *bhakti* movement in Southern India crystallised the idea of a temple as the focus of devotion to allow the collective participation of all members of society irrespective of their social position. It was because of this reasoning that pilgrimage emerged as a socio-cultural institution, where each site with its individual history, legends, rituals, and deities became associated with the collective consciousness of the community (Dutta 2010). The *Divyadeśams* established the legitimacy of *Śrīvaiṣṇavism* by providing a solid practising platform and a launch pad for the fervent growth of the *Śrīvaiṣṇava* movement across the region, highly influencing the masses with its simplicity and ease of worship (Iyengar 2009). Temples in every size and place after being considered sanctified by the hymns of

the *Ālvār* saints, transformed from familial shrines and village centres to regional and pan-regional pilgrimage destinations. The *Nālāyirativviyapirapantam* became a reflection of a Tamil subregional identity, where most of the sites mentioned in the text having a concentration in the Kaveri basin, made the deltaic territory a Tamil circulatory region of importance (Stein 1997: 7-26). The *Divyadeśam* temples today are economic generators that form an important support structure for the areas surrounding them in terms of being the main source of income with some of the temples becoming popular tourist destinations in the region, attracting both national and international visitors. A study similar to what was attempted in this paper can be used for any traditional textual source written with a strict sense of geography in mind. All the tangible data that can be procured from such texts can be plotted using modern GIS softwares to give a visual idea of the boundaries that existed in the past which could then be used to compare and understand present and existing boundaries.

Appendix

Chola Nadu Temples

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
1	Srirangam	Tiruchirappali	Ranganatha Swamy Temple	10.86232	78.69034
2	Thirukozy	Tiruchirappali	Kamalavalli Nachiyar/Azhagiya Manavalar Temple	10.82635	78.6738
3	Thirukarambanoor	Tiruchirappali	Purushothaman Perumal Temple, Thirukkarambanoor	10.8773	78.70351
4	Thiruvellarai	Tiruchirappali	Pundarikaksha Perumal Temple	10.9561	78.6682
5	Thiruanbil	Thanjavur	Vadivazhagiya Nambi Perumal Temple	10.86787	78.88249
6	Thirupper nagar	Thanjavur	Appakkudathan Perumal Temple	10.8396	78.88964
7	Thirukkandiyur	Thanjavur	Hara Sabha Vimochana Perumal Temple	10.86036	79.10887
8	Thirukkoodalur	Thanjavur	Vaiyyam Kaatha Perumal Temple	10.92514	79.20385
9	Thirukkavithalam	Thanjavur	Gajendra Varadha Perumal Temple	10.94686	79.2572
10	Thiruppullam Boothankudi	Thanjavur	Valvil Ramar Perumal Temple	10.9718	79.30405
11	Thiru Aadhanoor	Thanjavur	Aandu Alakkum Ayan Perumal Temple	10.97642	79.31383
12	Thirukkudhanthai	Thanjavur	Sarangapani Temple	10.95939	79.37566
13	Thiruvinnagar	Thanjavur	Oppiliappan Temple	10.96139	79.43226
14	Thirunaraiyur	Thanjavur	Thirunarayoor Nambi Perumal Temple	10.91573	79.44615

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
15	Thiruccherai	Thanjavur	Saranathan Perumal Temple	10.87852	79.45488
16	Thirukkannamangai	Thiruvavur	Bhaktavatsala Perumal Temple	10.79929	79.58704
17	Thirukkanapuram	Nagapattinam	Neelamega Perumal Temple	10.86866	79.70441
18	Thirukkanangudi	Tirunelveli	Loganatha Perumal Temple	10.75651	79.76378
19	Thirunaagai	Viluppuram	Neelamega Perumal Temple	10.76079	79.84071
20.1	Thanjaimaamanikoil	Thanjavur	Neelamega Perumal Temple	10.81748	79.13584
20.2	Thanjaimaamanikoil	Thanjavur	Thanjai Mani Kundram Perumal	10.81676	79.13745
20.3	Thanjaimaamanikoil	Thanjavur	Thanjai Yazhinagar Temple	10.81576	79.13872
21	Thirunandhipura Vinnagaram	Thanjavur	Jaganatha Perumal Temple	10.92214	79.37185
22	Thiruvelliyankudi	Thanjavur	Kola Valvilli Ramar Perumal Temple	11.05651	79.44341
23	Thiruvazhunthoor	Thanjavur	Devaadi Raja Perumal Temple	11.04691	79.57997
24	Thiruchirupuliyur	Thanjavur	Arulmaakadal Perumal Temple	10.99083	79.6693
25	Thalaicchanga Nanmadiyam	Mayiladuthurai	Naan Madhiya Perumal Temple	11.12998	79.78543
26	Thiru Indhaloor	Mayiladuthurai	Parimala Ranganatha Perumal Temple	11.10986	79.64662
27	Thirunangur	Nagapattinam	Rajagopala Swamy Temple	11.19231	79.79607
28	Thirukkazhiseerama Vinnagaram	Nagapattinam	Thirivikrama Perumal Temple	11.24104	79.73161
29	Thiru Arimeya Vinnagaram	Nagapattinam	Pallikonda Perumal Temple	11.17661	79.77748
30	Thiruvanpurushothamam	Nagapattinam	Purushothama Perumal Temple	11.1787	79.77717
31	Thirusemponseikoil	Nagapattinam	Sempon Arangar Temple	11.17853	79.77968
32	Thiru Manimaada Kovil	Nagapattinam	Narayana Perumal Temple	11.17407	79.77724
33	Thiru Vaikuntha Vinnagaram	Nagapattinam	aigundha Nathan Perumal Temple	11.18005	79.77854
34.1	Thiruvali	Nagapattinam	Lakshmi Narashima Perumal Temple	11.20277	79.77416
34.2	Thirunagari	Nagapattinam	Vedharaja Perumal Temple	11.22651	79.80063
35	Thiru Thevanar Thogai	Nagapattinam	Deiva Naayaga Perumal Temple	11.19696	79.77563
36	Thiruthetriambalam	Nagapattinam	Seganmaal Ranganatha Perumal Temple	11.17661	79.77748
37	Thirumanikoodam	Nagapattinam	Varadharaja Perumal Temple	11.17986	79.78826
38	Thiruvellakulam	Nagapattinam	Srinivasa Perumal Temple	11.19025	79.76499
39	Thiruparthanpalli	Nagapattinam	Thamaraiyal Kelvan Perumal Temple	11.1702	79.79745
40	Thiruchitrakoodam	Cuddalore	Govindaraja Perumal Temple	11.39909	79.69354

Nadu Naadu Temples

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
41	Thiruvahindapuram	Cuddalore	Deyva Nayaga Perumal Temple	11.74481	79.70971
42	Thirukkiviloor	Villupuram	Thiruvikrama Perumal Temple	11.96712	79.2023

Thondai Nadu Temples

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
43	Thirukachchi	Kanchipuram	Varadharaja Perumal Temple	12.81823	79.72364
44	Ashtabhujagaram	Kanchipuram	Aadhikesava Perumal Temple	12.82255	79.71102"
45	Thiruthanka	Kanchipuram	Deepa Prakasar Perumal Temple	12.82436	79.70572
46	Thiruvellukai	Kanchipuram	Azhagiya Singar Perumal Temple	12.82203	79.70649
47	Thiruneeragam	Kanchipuram	Jagadeeshwarar Temple	12.83904	79.705
48	Thiruppadakam	Kanchipuram	Pandava Thoodhar Temple	12.84284	79.69724
49	Thirunlathingal Thundam	Kanchipuram	Nilathingal Thundathan Temple	12.84734	79.69967
50	Thiru Ooragam	Kanchipuram	Ulagalantha Perumal Temple	12.83894	79.70516
51	Thiruvekka	Kanchipuram	Yathothakaari Perumal Temple	12.82394	79.71257
52	Thirukaragam	Kanchipuram	Karunakara Perumal Temple	12.83916	79.70537
53	Thirukaarvanam	Kanchipuram	Thirukkaar Vaanar Temple	12.83925	79.70506
54	Thirukkalanoor	Kanchipuram	Aadhi Varaha Perumal Temple	12.8406	79.70305
55	Thirupavalavannam	Kanchipuram	Pavala Vannar Temple	12.84349	79.7075
56	Parameshwara Vinnagaram	Kanchipuram	Vaikunda Perumal Temple"	12.8372	"
57	Thiruputkuzhi	Kanchipuram	Vijayaraghava Perumal Temple	12.8726	79.61887
58	Thirunindravoor	Chennai	Bhaktavatsala Perumal Temple	13.11268	80.02658
59	Thiru Evvul	Chennai	Veeraraghava Perumal Temple	13.14294	79.90732
60	Thiruvallikeni	Chennai	Parthasarathyswamy Temple	13.05378	80.2769
61	Thiruneermalai	Chennai	Neervanna Perumal Temple	12.96247	80.11377
62	Thiruvidadventhai	Chennai	Nithya Kalyana Perumal Temple	12.76296	80.2425
63	Thirukadalmalai	Chengalpattu	Sthala Sayana Perumal Temple	12.6174	80.19336
64	Thirukkadigai	Ranipet	Yoga Narasimha Swamy Temple	13.08825	79.41853

Vada Nadu Temples

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
65	Thiruayoddhi	Ayodhya	Shri Ram Mandir Ayodhya	26.79557	82.19441
66	Thirunaimisaranayam	Sitapur	Devaraja Perumal Temple	27.34985	80.48363
67	Thiruppirudi	Chamoli	Paramapurusha Perumal Temple	30.55617	79.56629
68	Thirukandam	Tehri Garhwal	Neelamega Perumal Raghunath ji Temple	30.1461	78.59832
69	Thiruvadriashramam	Chamoli	Badri Narayana Perumal Temple	30.74444	79.49111
70	Salagramam	Mustang (Nepal)	Moorthy Perumal (Mukthinath) Temple	28.81661	83.87193
71	Thiru Vadamadurai	Mathura	Krishna Janm bhoomi Temple	27.50497	77.6697

No.	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
72	Thiruvaipadi	Mathura	Gokul Temple	27.42937	77.71398
73	Thiru Dwarakai	Devbumhi Dwaraka	Dwarkadhish Temple	22.23723	68.96758
74	Singavelkunram	Nandyal	Jwala Narasimhar Temple	15.1258	78.74469
75	Tirupathi	Chittor	Srinivasa Perumal Temple	13.68297	79.34813

Malai Nadu Temples

No	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
76	Thirunaavaya	Malappuram	Naavaay Mugundha Perumal Temple	10.86363	75.98198
77	Thiruvithuvakkodu	Palakkad	Uyyavantha Perumal Temple	10.78321	76.18421
78	Thirukatkarai	Ernakulam	Kaatkarai Appa Perumal Temple	10.03583	76.32963
79	Thirumoozhikalam	Ernakulam	Moozhikkalathaan Perumal Temple	10.18804	76.32749
80	Tiruvallavazh	Pathanamthitta	Sree Vallabha Temple	9.37435	76.56224
81	Thirukodithanam	Kottayam	Thrickodithanam MahaViṣṇu Temple	9.43829	76.56237
82	Thiruchengannur	Alappuzha	Thrichittat MahaViṣṇu Temple	9.32631	76.60444
83	Thirupuliyur	Alappuzha	Thirupuliyoor MahaViṣṇu Temple	9.30169	76.58635
84	Thiruvaaranvilai	Pathanamthitta	Aranmula Parthasarathy Temple	9.3285	76.68833
85	Thiruvanvandoor	Alappuzha	Thiruvanvandoor Sree MahaViṣṇu Temple	9.34298	76.58073
86	Thiruvananthapuram	Thiruvananthapuram	Sree Padmanabhaswamy Temple	8.48202	76.94442
87	Thiruvattaru	Kanyakumari	Aadhikesava Perumal Temple	8.32982	77.26535
88	Thiruvanparisaaram	Kanyakumari	Kuralappa Perumal Temple	8.20818	77.44764

Pandiya Nadu Temples

No	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
89	Thirukurungudi	Thirunelveli	Arulmigu Thiru Vaishnava Nambi Temple	8.43684	77.56701
90	Thiruccherivaramangai	Thirunelveli	Thothatrinatha Perumal Temple	8.49223	77.65797
91	Thiruvaikundam	Thoothukudi	Vaikundanatha Perumal Temple	8.63101	77.91031
92	Thiruvargunamangai	Thoothukudi	Vijayaasana Perumal Temple	8.63724	77.92437
93	Thiruppulingudi	Thoothukudi	Kaaisinavendhar Perumal Temple	8.63951	77.93332
94.1	Thirutholaivillimangalam	Thoothukudi	Irettai Thirupathi Sri Srinivasa Perumal Temple	8.60928	77.97357
94.2	Thirutholaivillimangalam	Thoothukudi	Irettai Thirupathi Sri Aravindha Lochana Perumal Temple	8.61187	77.97314
95	Thirukkulanthai	Thoothukudi	Arulmigu Sri Mayakoothar Temple	8.64196	77.99447
96	Tirukkolor	Thoothukudi	Vaithamanidhi Perumal Temple	8.59706	77.95863
97	Thirupperai	Thoothukudi	Makara Nedunkulai Kaathar Perumal Temple	8.60321	77.9867

No	Name	District	Temple Name	Latitude	Longitude
98	Thirukkurugoor	Virudhunagar	Aadhinatha Aazhwar Temple	8.60743	77.93876
99	Thiruvilliputthur	Virudhunagar	Vadabadrasai Perumal Temple	9.50893	77.63245
100	Thiruthangal	Virudhunagar	Nindra Narayana Perumal Temple	9.48168	77.81174
101	Thirukoodal	Madurai	Koodal Azhagar Perumal Temple	9.91394	78.11423
102	Thirumaaliruncholai	Madurai	Kallazhagar Perumal Temple	10.07416	78.21361
103	Thirumogur	Madurai	Kaalamegha Perumal Temple	9.95044	78.20787
104	Thirukottiyur	Sivaganga	Sowmiya Narayana Perumal Temple	10.0604	78.56089
105	Thirupullani	Ramanathapuram	Aadhi Jagannatha Perumal Temple	9.2833	78.82482
106	Thirumeyyam	Pudukkottai	Sathyagiri Natha Perumal Temple	10.24668	78.75214

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